

THE PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD -N·C·S-. PART VII. A RE-INVESTIGATION OF THE EXTENT ON SOME HYDROLYTIC DECOMPOSITIONS OF PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE. REACTIONS OF SODIUM ETHOXIDE ON PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDE AND OF ACETIC ANHYDRIDE AND HYDROLYTIC AGENTS ON $\alpha\alpha'$ - AND $\alpha\beta$ - METHYLPHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES.

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In continuation of previous hydrolytic studies upon phenylthiocarbamide (I), some of which needed reinvestigation, it became desirable to extend the hydrolytic reactions to the *unsym*- (II) and *sym*. methyl (III) homologues of (I) and secondly try the action of (a) a strong alkali (NaOEt) on (I) and, (b) a strong acidic reagent (Ac₂O) on (II) and (III) respectively. (a) in presence of alcohol yields hydrogen sulphide and phenylcyanamide but the reaction is otherwise in its absence. This, together with reactions of (II) show the importance of the hydrogen atom of the anilino group in this change. (III) resembles (I) in its reactions but (II) differs from either of these in the case of its decomposition with various reagents. Results recorded for (I)-(II) indicate that increasing acidity does not effect the hydrolytic decomposition in the manner supposed previously.

Hydrolytic agents decompose phenylthiocarbamide (Mehta and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 635) into hydrogen sulphide and phenylcyanamide, aniline and thiocyanic acid, ammonia and phenylmustard oil, thus :

and the extent of each of these changes was found to depend upon the acidity of the medium. Later, however, evidence accumulated to show that analytical difficulties had led to some erroneous conclusions with regard to changes (ii) and (iii) which are now reinvestigated. Further, the behaviour of phenylthiocarbamide towards sodium ethoxide and of $\alpha\alpha'$ - and $\alpha\beta$ -methylphenylthiocarbamides towards acidic reagents, water and alkali have been studied for comparison. To estimate small amount of thiocyanic acid formed as in (ii) in presence of phenylthiocarbamide two methods

have now been devised, one of which depends on the ready formation of a nickel tetrapyrroline thiocyanate complex $[\text{NiPy}_4(\text{CNS})_2]$ (Spacu, *Bull. Soc. Stiinta Cluj*, 1922, 1, 314; 1923, 2, 585) which also has the advantage of being applicable in presence of chlorides, and the other on the removal of phenylthiocarbamide from solution by ammoniacal silver nitrate (*vide* experimental) which can also be utilised to estimate small amount of mustard oil produced in change (iii).

The results obtained by these methods show that change (ii) is 2-5 % in one hour and increasing acidity does not materially increase the change. Also, change (iii) can occur to a small extent in aqueous solution as well as in presence of strong acids.

When alcoholic solutions of phenylthiocarbamide and sodium ethoxide are mixed and boiled, considerable sulphide is produced according to change (i). In the absence of alcohol, however, if the residue, supposed to contain the sodium salt of the thiocarbamide, be carefully heated, a residue of sodium sulphide is not produced appreciably, sodium thiocyanate predominating, and complex decompositions like those obtained by dry-heating phenylthiocarbamide alone (Davis and Underwood, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2802) occur.

$\alpha\alpha'$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide exhibits a striking contrast with the behaviour of either the parent phenylthiocarbamide or the *sym.* isomer in the ease with which it is decomposed by the various reagents. Thus when boiled with acetic anhydride, *N*-hydrochloric acid, water or *N*-sodium hydroxide it decomposes mainly into methylaniline and thiocyanic acid

which occurs on mere dissolution in the first reagent. With the aqueous acid the change in one hour takes place twice as rapidly (37%) as with alkali (17%) and in both cases is greater than in water (9%). Little hydrogen sulphide is produced in alkaline solutions.

Acetic anhydride, hydrochloric acid, and water decompose $\alpha\beta$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide into phenylmustard oil and only traces of methyl mustard oil :

The change with acetic anhydride is maximum after six minutes (70%) and appears to take place through the initial formation of the acetyl compound of the thiocarbamide (*cf.* Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 89, 396). With

the aqueous acid, however, it is slow (5.4% in 1 hour) and more so with water. When boiled with alkali, sulphide is produced (12%) and from analogy with the parent compound it is expected to be formed thus :

Traces of aniline, methylamine, polysulphides have been found but we have not identified the above cyanamide nor the oxygen urea from it which is expected to be the product of such reactions.

These experiments show a formal similarity in the behaviour of $\alpha\beta$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide and phenylthiocarbamide. In the latter case the slight diminution of change (ii) in relatively concentrated acid or in water is analogous to that observed by Fawsitt with methyl-, and $\alpha\alpha'$ -dimethyl carbamides (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1584, ; 1905, 87, 474) but the explanations advanced by him to account for such results do not generally fit in our case with the *unsym.*-methyl homologue. The possibility of salt formation to some extent in acid solution cannot, however, be overlooked and it is likely that the cation so formed, with its electro-meric change (*cf. Lecher, Annalen*, 1925, 448, 35) determines the extent of such decompositions as (ii) and (iii).

Comparing the reactions of sodium ethoxide in the presence of alcohol and on dry heating with phenylthiocarbamide it appears that it is the hydrogen of the anilino group of the thiocarbamide and for that matter of the *sym.* compound, which is concerned in the formation of hydrogen sulphide and a cyanamide derivative, the functioning of this hydrogen atom being suppressed in the absence of a solvent. This view is amply supported by the behaviour of $\alpha\alpha'$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide under like conditions.

In all acidic and aqueous hydrolytic experiments a small amount of carbon oxysulphide is invariably formed which is not accounted for by the decomposition of thiocyanic acid or of mustard oil under the conditions of experiment. This fact taken in conjunction with the reaction of acetic anhydride throws a doubt on the view that thiocyanic acid or mustard oil is produced by the spontaneous dissociation of the thiocarbamide in solution into neutral molecules. Evidently there is some chemical combination with the solvent. Fearon (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 1652) has shown that

cyanic acid is only a dehydration product of carbamic acid during the zymolysis of urea.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydrolytic Experiments with Phenylthiocarbamide: Procedure and Methods of Analysis.

Estimation of Thiocyanic Acid. (a).—To precipitate out nickel tetrapyrroline thiocyanate $[\text{NiPy}_4(\text{CNS})_2]$ (Spacu, *loc. cit.*), the slightly acid aqueous solution containing the thiocyanate (up to 0.1 g. CNS' in 150 c.c.) was treated in a 250 c. c. flask with pyridine (7.5 c.c.) and a known excess of 0.1 N-nickel sulphate (10-20 c. c.) till the supernatant liquid acquired after the settling of the precipitate a bluish tinge. The liquid was then made upto 250 c. c. with water, mixed, and filtered through a dry filter into a separating funnel. Traces of the complex were removed from solution by extracting thrice with chloroform (5 c. c.) which did not affect excess of nickel present otherwise. For determining the latter, 200 c. c. of the solution were treated with moderate excess of 2 N-sodium hydroxide which precipitated nickelous hydroxide quantitatively from aqueous pyridine solution. Phenylthiocarbamide and moderate amount of aniline did not interfere but diphenylguanidine did. The precipitate was washed free of phenylthiocarbamide and chloride by hot dilute solution of potassium nitrate, redissolved into a 250 c.c. flask by warm dilute nitric acid and the solution made barely acid. Nickel was estimated in the latter solution by again precipitating the thiocyanate complex (*cf.* Dobbins and Sanders, *Ing. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1934, 6, 459) with 0.1 N-potassium thiocyanate, pyridine (3 c.c.) and excess of potassium thiocyanate in an aliquote of 100 c.c. liquid titrated back with silver nitrate.

(b) The thiocarbamide present in slightly acid aqueous solution containing upto 0.1 g. of CNS' in 100-150 c. c. solution was desulphurised with N-silver nitrate (3.4 c. c.) in presence of 8% ammonia (60 c. c.) and the mixture heated at 80° for 1 hour. On cooling, excess of silver was removed by passing hydrogen sulphide for a few seconds through the ammoniacal solution. The latter was immediately freed of hydrogen sulphide by addition of slight excess of cadmium sulphate, filtered from insoluble matter and neutralised with nitric acid, adding 2 c. c. in excess. The thiocyanic acid was then estimated by adding excess of 0.1 N-silver nitrate and titrating back with 0.1 N-potassium thiocyanate. The results by these two methods agreed closely and were accurate.

Estimation of Phenylmustard Oil.—The thiocarbamide was steam dis-

tilled in the presence of the hydrolytic agent and the aqueous distillate (150-200 c. c. for 1 hr.) treated with *N*-silver nitrate (5.5 c. c.), 8% ammonia (60 c. c.) and heated under reflux at 80° for 2 hours. The precipitated silver sulphide was weighed on a tared filter paper and the amount of mustard oil calculated.

Detection and Determination of Carbon Oxysulphide.—The upper end of the reflux condenser was connected with 5 absorption tubes containing in order strongly acidified copper sulphate solution (10 c. c.), 33% aqueous caustic potash solution (8 c. c.), pyridine (5 c. c.) and finally alcoholic caustic potash (1 g. KOH + 2 c. c. water + 2 c. c. alcohol; 15 c. c. and 10 c. c.). At the end of boiling, the air in the apparatus was driven through the above reagents by aspiration. The alcoholic solutions were mixed and concentrated, oxidised with bromine water and the sulphate so formed was estimated. Ammonium thiocyanate solution when boiled with excess of *N*-hydrochloric acid gave no sulphate, whilst with phenylmustard oil it was negligible.

Estimation of Ammonia in Aqueous Hydrolytic Liquors.—This depended on the observation of Foreman (*Biochem. J.*, 1920, 14, 451; Gortner, "Outlines of Biochemistry", 1929, p. 328) that in 85% alcohol the salts of ammonia and amines with strong acids behave as free acids. Two samples (20 g.) were taken. In one free acid was determined by titration with alkali, and in the other absolute alcohol (180 c. c.) was added to make a 85% solution. The latter was titrated with alkali (*N*/40) using phenolphthalein as indicator. The difference gave the amount of ammonia in solution.

Table I records the results obtained by above methods on treating phenyl-carbamide (5 g.) with an equivalent of the hydrolytic agent in concentrations stated therein. The figures (mols./100 mols. thiocarbamide) for carbon oxysulphide are for 2 hours' and the rest for 1 hour's boiling.

TABLE I.

	Dilution of carbamide and hydrolytic agent.	Hydrolytic agents		
		HCl.	Water.	NaOH.
Thiocyanic acid	1.00N	2.5	1.9	3.1
	0.66	4.0	2.6	...
	0.25	5.4	3.8	...
Phenylmustard oil	0.66	1.4	...	...
	0.25	...	1.3	...
Carbon oxysulphide	0.66	3.1	...	...
	0.25	...	2.4	...

In *N*-aqueous and acidic solutions some of the substance remained undissolved. In another experiment a 0.25 *N*-aqueous solution of phenylthiocarbamide was boiled for 2 hours and ammonia and carbon oxysulphide also estimated (Found: HCNS, 6.7; PhNCS, 3.0; COS, 1.4; NH₃, 5%). During boiling, thiocarbanilide (3%) often got deposited on the inside of the reflux condenser tubing. Thus, the occurrence of decomposition of the thiocarbamide into ammonia and phenylmustard oil even in aqueous solutions was clearly demonstrated.

Phenylthiocarbamide and Sodium Ethoxide.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c. c.) was boiled with sodium (1.15 g.) in alcohol (30 c. c.) for 2 hours. No ammoniacal or any other odour came and the alcoholic solution contained sulphide and traces of thiocyanic acid. (Found: H₂S, 15; HCNS, 0.2%). In another experiment the alcohol was evaporated off and the residue dry-heated. The distillate contained traces of ammonia, aniline and thiocarbanilide and the residue contained sodium thiocyanate and traces of sulphide. On heating at a lower temperature (135-45°) for 2 hours, few drops of oil appeared in the distillate and a little subimate was formed (ammonium sulphide). The residue contained thiocarbanilide, aniline, sulphide and sodium thiocyanate. (Found: H₂S, 12; HCNS, 64%). The last was the main product (Found: CNS', 71.2. NaCNS requires CNS', 71.6 per cent) that crystallised out on concentrating an alcoholic extract of the residue.

Hydrolytic Experiments with the Methylphenylthiocarbamides.

α'-Methylphenylthiocarbamide and Acetic Anhydride.—The thiocarbamide (8.3 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 g.) were boiled under reflux for 3.15 minutes. The reddish solution contained methylaniline and thiocyanic acid which decomposed on longer heating. The acetyl compound of Doran and Dixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 339) was not identified in this experiment nor could it be prepared by Hegershoff's method (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3649).

α'-Methylphenylthiocarbamide and N-Hydrochloric Acid, Water and N-Sodium Hydroxide.—The thiocarbamide (8.3 g.) was refluxed with each of the above hydrolytic agents (50 c. c.) for 1 hour. The reaction mixture, which smelt of methylaniline in the last two cases, was cooled and analysed for thiocyanic acid (Volhard's method) and the results were checked by colourimetric measurements and estimating residual alkalinity respectively. Traces of hydrogen sulphide formed in the last case were also estimated.

TABLE II.

Hydrolytic agent.	Thiocyanic acid.	Hydrogen sulphide.
Hydrochloric acid	37	Traces.
Water	8.5	Nil
Sodium hydroxide	17.0	1.2

These changes were halved in $N/4$ solutions. In a similar experiment with N -alkali the boiling was done for 4 hours. (Found HCNS, 50; H_2S , 7%).

$\alpha\beta$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide and Acetic Anhydride.—The thiocarbamide (8.3 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 g.) were boiled for 3-15 minutes. The mustard oil formed was steam distilled and weighed.

TABLE III.

Time (min.)	...	3	6	10	15
Mustard oil (g.)	...	3.3	4.4	3.35	1.15

The yield of the oil diminished after six minutes due to the secondary change namely

and acetanilide was present in the residual mixture after 4-5 minutes. Below 3 minutes a solid (m. p. 82°) could be isolated and was found to be identical with the acetyl derivative of the thiocarbamide prepared by Hugesshoff's method (*loc. cit.*), m. p. and mixed m.p. 82° .

In the above experiments the mother liquors smelt of methylamine on warming with alkali. Also, on distilling together the four samples of mustard oil few drops of oil of b. p. $116-125^\circ$ were obtained and were shown to contain methylmustard oil after conversion into $\alpha\beta$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide. The latter formed an unstable yellow nitroso derivative (separate communication) with aqueous sodium nitrite and acetic acid. Thiocarbamide apparently did not react under these conditions.

$\alpha\beta$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide and Hydrochloric Acid and Water.—The thiocarbamide (5.53 g.) and N -Hydrochloric acid (33 c. c.) diluted to 50 c. c. were steam distilled for 1 hour and the distillate treated with ammoniacal silver nitrate as in the case of the parent compound (Found: Ag_2S , 5.4%). In another experiment the distillate was extracted with chloroform and the oil converted into thiocarbamides. Mostly thiocarbamide

was formed whilst small amount of $\alpha\beta$ -methylphenylthiocarbamide was also shown to be present as in the case of acetic anhydride. The residual mixture smelt of methylamine on basification and no emulsion of aniline was visible.

With water (50 c. c.) there was hardly any change but on dilution (132 c.c.) few drops of mustard oils came over in the steam distillate (Found: Ag_2S , 2%).

$\alpha\beta$ -Methylphenylthiocarbamide and N-Sodium Hydroxide.—The thiocarbamide (5.53 g.) and alkali (33 c. c.) were refluxed together for 1 hour. Traces of methylamine and aniline were produced, whilst the alkaline reaction mixture contained mainly unchanged thiocarbamide and sulphide (Found: H_2S , 12%). The estimation of the latter by titration with alkaline zinc solution presented difficulty because nickel sulphate which was used as an external indicator gave a persistent yellow colouration at the end-point. This was also verified on a large scale and showed the presence of traces of polysulphides (*cf.* Mermet, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1875, ii, 24, 433). To get a control over the above figure, the precipitated zinc sulphide was filtered, washed and estimated iodometrically (Found: H_2S , 17%). On prolonged boiling (4 hours) the alkaline solution contained more sulphide (35%), unchanged thiocarbamide and polysulphides (traces) and smelt appreciably of aniline and methylamine, but no other product was found.

With $\alpha\alpha$ - and $\alpha\beta$ -methylphenylthiocarbamides carbon oxysulphide was detected as in the case of the parent compound but was not estimated.